

Synthesis, antibacterial, antifungal and cytotoxicity screening of 1,5-benzodiazepines

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Abstract : In our present study we have synthesized a series of 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) by the reaction of a series of (*E*)-thienyl chalcones (**3a-l**) with *o*-phenylene diamine using piperidine and acetic acid as catalyst. (*E*)-Thienyl chalcones (**3a-l**) were prepared by the reaction of thiophene-2-aldehyde (**1**) with a series of substituted acetophenones (**2**) in the presence of sodium hydroxide. The structure of the synthesized compounds was confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, Mass spectroscopy and elemental analysis further the compounds (**4a-l**) were tested for their antibacterial, antifungal and cytotoxic potential.

Keywords : Benzodiazepines, antibacterial, antifungal, cytotoxic activity.

Introduction

The literature survey revealed that benzodiazepine derivatives possess wide range of pharmacological activity such as antipsychotic, anticonvulsant¹, anticancer², antimicrobial, anthelmintic³, analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic activity⁴.

Chalcones are a class of α , β unsaturated ketones and these molecules on reaction with suitable cyclising agents can further be cyclised into various five, six and seven membered heterocyclic compounds. The synthesis of pyrimidines⁵⁻⁷ and pyrazolines⁸ via a series of (*E*)-thienyl chalcones (**3a-l**) in our recent publications and the same chalcones have also been utilized in the present study to synthesize 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**).

Based on the above observations it was contemplated to synthesize 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) and screen for their antibacterial, antifungal and cytotoxic potential.

Results and discussion

Chalcones (**3a-l**) were prepared by the reaction of thiophene-2-aldehyde (**1**) with a series of substituted

acetophenones (**2**) in the presence of sodium hydroxide. The *J* values between H α -H β protons in ¹H NMR spectra was observed in the range of 15.1–15.7 Hz and CH=CH *def*, in IR spectra was observed in the range of 957–975 cm⁻¹, which confirms that the synthesized chalcones (**3a-l**)⁹ were geometrically pure and were of *trans*-configuration. Further the chalcones (**3a-l**) were treated with *o*-phenylene diamine to yield 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**)¹⁰ with the formation of a chiral centre at C-2 position of benzodiazepine ring (Fig. 1).

The synthesized 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) were tested for their antibacterial potential against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, antifungal potential against yeast and mold (Table 1) and cytotoxic activity against Dalton's lymphoma ascites cell lines (DAC) by trypan blue dye exclusion assay (Table 2).

Among the 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) screened for antimicrobial activity compounds **4b**, **4f**, **4h** and **4i** have shown moderate antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria and compounds **4b**, **4d**, **4e**, **4f**, **4h** and **4i** have exhibited significant antifungal activity both against

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme for synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines (4a-l).

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal screening of compounds (4a-l) by tube dilution method

Compd.	R	Minimum inhibitory concentration (µg)					
		<i>E. fecalis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>
4a	4-NO ₂	62.5	R	31.2	62.5	31.2	16.6
4b	4-Cl	16.6	31.2	62.5	62.5	31.2	8.3
4c	4-CH ₃	31.2	16.6	62.5	31.2	62.5	16.6
4d	4-NH ₂	62.5	31.2	62.5	16.6	16.6	8.3
4e	H	31.2	62.5	62.5	31.2	16.6	31.2
4f	4-F	8.3	16.6	R	31.2	8.3	16.6
4g	3-NO ₂	R	R	62.5	R	31.2	16.6
4h	4-Br	16.6	8.3	31.2	62.5	4.1	8.3
4i	4-OCH ₃	16.6	31.2	R	31.2	8.3	8.3
4j	4-OH	31.2	16.6	62.5	62.5	31.2	62.5
4k	1-Naphthyl	R	R	62.5	R	62.5	31.2
4l	2-Thiophene	R	R	R	62.5	31.2	62.5
Std.	Ciprofloxacin	1 µg	2 µg	1 µg	2 µg	-	-
	Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	16.6 µg	8.3 µg

R : Resistant.

yeast and mold. Further the compounds **4c** and **4e** have showed significant cytotoxic activity with 78 and 95% cell death at 200 µg/ml concentration respectively.

Experimental

The IR spectrum was recorded by using Bruker Alpha FTIR spectrometer using KBr pellet technique. Bruker Avance II 400 MHz NMR spectrometer was used to record ¹H NMR spectra using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded using Electrospray ionization method on Shimadzu LCMS-2010 EV Mass spectrometer. Open capillary method was used to determine melting points. Carlo Elba

1108 analyzer was used for elemental analysis.

Synthesis of (E)-thienyl chalcones (3a-l) :

Thiophene-2-carbaldehyde (1.12 g, 0.01 mol) was stirred with various substituted acetophenones (0.01 mol) in rectified spirit (25 ml) and using sodium hydroxide as catalyst for 24 h in ice cold conditions. The resultant mixture was poured slowly with stirring in a beaker containing crushed ice. Dilute hydrochloric acid was added dropwise until the mixture turned acidic. The resultant solid product was separated by filtration and was purified by recrystallization using ethyl alcohol.

3a : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 70%; Molecular

Table 2. Cytotoxicity screening of compounds (**4a-l**) by trypan blue dye exclusion method

Compd.	R	Percent cell death at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)				
		10	20	50	100	200
4a	4-NO ₂	0	0	5	9	19
4b	4-Cl	4	9	18	24	40
4c	4-CH ₃	10	16	38	50	78
4d	4-NH ₂	0	4	8	15	34
4e	H	12	38	72	88	95
4f	4-F	0	2	6	13	23
4g	3-NO ₂	0	0	4	14	38
4h	4-Br	0	4	8	12	24
4i	4-OCH ₃	0	10	14	20	30
4j	4-OH	0	0	0	2	8
4k	Naphthyl	0	10	22	31	52
4l	Thienyl	0	0	6	10	22
5-Fluorouracil		9	22	36	51	93

formula : C₁₃H₉NO₃S, m.p. 140–142 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 60.22 (60.19); H, 3.50 (3.48); N, 5.40 (5.37).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3097 (Ar C-H), 1653 (C=O), 1574 (C=C), 1320, 1520 (Ar-NO₂), 972 (*trans* CH=CH *def*), 708 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.34 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, CH=CH), 7.56 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, CH=CH), 7.14 (1H, m, thiophene-H); Mass : 259 (M⁺).

3b : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 68%; Molecular formula : C₁₃H₉ClOS, m.p. 146–148 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 62.78 (62.71); H, 3.65 (3.62).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3082 (Ar CH), 1653 (C=O), 1589 (C=C), 971 (*trans* CH=CH *def*), 713 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.34 (2H, d, *J* 8.9 Hz, Ar-H), 8.12 (2H, d, *J* 8.9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, CH=CH), 7.49 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.26 (1H, d, *J* 15.1 Hz, CH=CH), 7.12–7.14 (1H, m, thiophene-H); Mass : 249 (M⁺).

3c : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 60%; Molecular formula : C₁₄H₁₂OS, m.p. 152–154 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 73.65 (73.56); H, 5.27 (4.84).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3096 (Aromatic CH), 2924 (Aliphatic CH),

1654 (C=O), 1577 (C=C), 960 (*trans* CH=CH *def*), 713 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 15.1 Hz, CH=CH), 7.91 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 3.4 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.31 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.26 (1H, d, *J* 15.1 Hz, CH=CH), 7.08–7.10 (1H, m, thiophene-H), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃); Mass : 229 (M⁺).

3d : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 73%; Molecular formula : C₁₃H₁₁NOS, m.p. 104–106 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 68.09 (68.02); H, 4.84 (4.81); N, 6.11 (6.09).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3427 (NH₂), 3319 (NH), 3101 (Aromatic CH), 1654 (C=O), 1598 (C=C), 957 (*trans* CH=CH *def*), 680 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 7.89 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CH), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.06 (1H, m, thiophene-H), 6.68 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.64 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, CH=CH), 4.16 (2H, s, NH₂); Mass : 230 (M⁺).

3e : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 50%; Molecular formula : C₁₃H₁₀OS, m.p. 124–126 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 72.87 (72.83); H, 4.70 (4.66).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3095 (Aromatic CH), 1656 (C=O), 1577 (C=C), 963 (*trans* CH=CH *def*), 1518 (Ar-NO₂ Ass.), 1319 (Ar-NO₂ Sym), 705 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.10 (1H, d, *J* 5.3 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, CH=CH), 7.89 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.74 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, thiophene-H), 7.68 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.61 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, CH=CH), 7.23 (1H, m, thiophene-H); Mass : 214 (M⁺).

Synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) :

(*E*)-Thienyl chalcones (0.01 mol) (**3a-l**) were refluxed with *o*-phenylene diamine (0.02 mol) in ethanol in the presence of piperidine and acetic acid for a period of about 8 h. The solvent was separated from the reaction mixture by distillation. Solid product separated out from the reaction mixture after it was set aside overnight. The product was filtered at pump and was washed with a small amount of ice cold ethyl alcohol.

4a : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 70%; Molecular formula : C₁₉H₁₅N₃O₂S, m.p. 181–182 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 65.31 (65.24); H, 4.33 (4.29); N, 12.03 (11.97).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3385 (NH), 3082 (Aromatic CH), 2881 (Aliphatic CH), 1635 (Aromatic C=C), 1588 (C=N), 1502, 1417 (Ar-NO₂), 1243 (C-N), 706 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 7.15–8.37 (11H, m, Ar), 8.09 (1H, s, NH), 3.35 (2H, d, CH₂ of benzodiazepine), 2.54–2.55 (1H, m, CH of benzodiazepine); Mass : 349 (M⁺).

4b : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 68%; Molecular formula : C₁₉H₁₅ClN₂S, m.p. 133–134 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 67.35 (67.33); H, 4.46 (4.42); N, 8.27 (8.21).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3339 (NH), 3067 (Aromatic CH), 2943 (Aliphatic CH), 1680 (Aromatic C=C), 1650 (C=N), 1218 (C-N), 709 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 6.41–7.21 (11H, m, Ar), 8.09 (1H, s, NH), 3.37 (2H, d, CH₂ of benzodiazepine), 3.04–3.09 (1H, m, CH of benzodiazepine); Mass : 338 (M⁺).

4c : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 60%; Molecular formula : C₂₀H₁₈N₂S, m.p. 164–165 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 75.44 (75.41); H, 5.70 (5.66); N, 8.80 (8.71).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3341 (NH), 3032 (Aromatic CH), 2922 (Aliphatic CH), 1652 (Aromatic C=C), 1584 (C=N), 1215 (C-N), 699 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 7.11–7.93 (11H, m, Ar), 7.86 (1H, s, NH), 3.29 (2H, d, CH₂ of benzodiazepine), 2.56–2.57 (1H, m, CH of benzodiazepine), 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃); Mass : 318 (M⁺).

4d : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 73%; Molecular formula : C₁₉H₁₇N₃S, m.p. 141–142 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (found) : C, 71.44 (71.38); H, 5.36 (5.29); N, 13.15 (13.08).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3469, 3202 (NH), 3060 (Ar. CH), 2881 (Aliphatic CH), 1640 (Ar. C=C), 1598 (C=N), 1194 (C-N), 707 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.04 (1H, s, NH), 6.64–7.82 (11H, m, Ar), 3.36 (2H, d, CH₂ of benzodiazepine), 2.54–2.55 (1H, m, CH of benzodiazepine); Mass : 319 (M⁺).

4e : Physical state : Solid; Yield : 50%; Molecular formula : C₁₉H₁₆N₂S, m.p. 159–160 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) : C, 74.97 (74.91); H, 5.30 (5.24); N, 9.20 (9.12).

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3341 (NH), 3036 (Aromatic CH), 2931 (Aliphatic CH), 1665 (Aromatic C=C), 1652 (C=N), 1235 (C-N), 725 (C-S); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 6.85–7.94

(12H, m, Ar), 8.55 (1H, s, NH), 3.85 (2H, d, CH₂ of benzodiazepine), 2.96–2.97 (1H, m, CH of benzodiazepine); Mass : 304 (M⁺).

Antimicrobial studies :

Tube dilution technique¹¹ was used to assess antibacterial and antifungal potential of 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**). Amoxicillin and Fluconazole were employed as the standard drug for the comparison of antibacterial and antifungal activity respectively. DMF was used as solvent control.

Cytotoxic activity :

Cytotoxic activity of 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) at 10, 20, 50, 100, 200 µg/ml concentrations was carried out using Dalton's lymphoma ascites (DAC) cells by trypan blue dye exclusion method¹².

Conclusion

The antimicrobial screening reveal that the synthesized 1,5-benzodiazepines (**4a-l**) can be good lead molecules as antifungal agents. The cytotoxicity screening reveal that compounds **4c** and **4e** can also be good lead molecules as anticancer agents and the literature survey reveals that these molecules exhibit anticancer activity by the inhibition of tubulin polymerization².

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References

1. R. Basawaraj, K. Naubade and S. S. Sangapure, *Ind. J. Het. Chem.*, 2008, **17**, 217.
2. A. Kamal, G. Balakishan, G. Ramakrishna, B. Shaik, K. Sreekanth, K. M. Balakrishna, M. Rajender, D. Dastagiri and V. K. Shasi, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 3870.
3. R. Kumar and Y. C. Joshi, *ARKIVOC*, 2007, **xiii**, 142.
4. G. Grossi, M. D. Braccio, G. Roma, V. Ballabeni, M. Tognolini, F. Calcina and E. Barocelli, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **37**, 933.

5. M. M. Hussain, K. I. Bhat, B. C. Revannasiddappa and D. R. Bharathi, *Int. J. Drug Dev. & Res.*, 2013, **5**, 150.
6. M. M. Hussain, K. I. Bhat, B. C. Revannasiddappa and D. R. Bharathi, *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2013, **5**, 471.
7. M. M. Hussain, K. I. Bhat, B. C. Revannasiddappa and G. R. Nataraj, *Ind. J. Het. Chem.*, 2012, **22**, 159.
8. M. M. Hussain, K. I. Bhat, B. C. Revannasiddappa, M. T. Ekbote and G. R. Nataraj, *Ind. J. Het. Chem.*, 2013, **22**, 267.
9. K. Yali, W. Kan, C. E. Michael, H. Ernest, L. M. Susan, A. P. Mikell and L. B. Milton, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **18**, 971.
10. M. C. Rosa, S. Dionisia, A. Shibly, A. Kumar, O. Prakash, P. S. Shiv and E. Jose, *ARKIVOC*, 2006, **xiv**, 35.
11. Q. Sadaf, in "Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing Protocols", eds. S. Richard, S. M. Lynn and A. C. Goodwin, CRC Press, Taylor and Francis Group, 2007, p. 75.
12. R. Kuttan, P. Bhanumathy, K. Nirmala and M. C. George, *Cancer Lett.*, 1985, **29**, 197.